

Magnesium Sulphate as an Effective adjuvant for Postoperative Pain Management in Lower Limb Orthopaedic SurgeriesShahzad Akhter¹, Kumar Shailesh², Mahesh Kumar³¹Assistant Professor, Dept. Of Anaesthesiology, JLN MCH, Bhagalpur²Senior Resident, Dept. of Anaesthesiology, JLN medical College, Bhagalpur³Associate Professor and Head of Department, Dept. of Anaesthesiology, JLN medical College, Bhagalpur

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kumar Shailesh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objective:** To observe the total analgesic requirement in the first 24 hrs of the postoperative period, if there is any prolongation of the time to rescue analgesia and incidence of complications in patients given Magnesium sulphate and the control group.**Methods:** The study comprised 50 patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgery who were ASA Grade I & II and were between the age of 20 and 65. After receiving spinal anaesthesia, 25 of these patients (Group A) got Magnesium Sulphate at a dose of 50 mg/kg in 100 ml bottles of normal saline, while the other 25 patients (Group B) received only NS (Group B). It was recorded when the first dose of analgesia was needed. Patients were watched for signs of sedation, hypotension, shivering, nausea, vomiting and pruritus. The total amount of analgesics needed in the first 24 hours following the operation was noted.**Results:** In Group A and Group B, the mean \pm SD of the time to rescue analgesia was 444 \pm 130 minutes and 287 \pm 55 minutes, respectively. The total analgesic requirement of Group A was significantly less as compared to Group B in the first 24 hours of the surgery. Incidence of complications were not significantly higher in the study group.**Conclusion:** We come to the conclusion that patients receiving spinal anaesthesia for lower limb orthopaedic procedures can safely receive IV magnesium sulphate in a bolus dose of 50mg/kg to reduce initial postoperative pain with a minimal incidence of complications.**Keywords:** Magnesium Sulphate, Postoperative Pain Management, Spinal Anaesthesia.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The International Association for the Study of Pain defines pain as "an uncomfortable, sensory, and emotional experience related to actual or potential tissue damage or explained in terms of such damage. [1] It is common to undertreat postoperative pain that results from inflammation brought on by tissue trauma or direct nerve injury. After surgery, it's critical to maintain good pain management to avoid complications like tachycardia, hypertension, immobility, deep venous thrombosis, and slow wound healing. [2] Starting physiotherapy and ambulation as soon as possible after surgery promotes quick healing and patient satisfaction. Adequate postoperative pain management is crucial for both the recovery from surgery and the avoidance of chronic postsurgical pain. [3] As a result, an essential part of postoperative healing is appropriately controlling postoperative pain. [4] This is because adequate pain control reduces perioperative morbidity by effectively blunting autonomic, somatic, and endocrine reactions.

Orthopaedic surgeries including total knee replacement, lower limb fractures, and arthroscopic ligament repairs result in acute postoperative pain that requires proper management to reduce complications and speed healing. By addressing acute pain head - on, central sensitization can be prevented.

Opioids are currently among the most popular and effective analgesics for the management of moderate to severe pain due to their potency and rapid onset of action. Opioid use has drawbacks due to the wide range of potential side effects, including urinary retention, pruritus, respiratory depression, changes in gastrointestinal motility that can cause constipation or diarrhoea, depression of the central nervous system, nausea or vomiting. The use of PCA pumps to administer opioids is linked to opioid addiction and dependency. [5-9]

Drugs classified as adjuvants are those that may help with pain management, but they are not often classified as analgesics. Ketamine, pregabalin, gabapentin, intravenous lidocaine, Alpha-2 - adrenoceptor agonists like clonidine and dexme-

detomidine, and magnesium sulphate are a few examples of these adjuvant analgesics. [2]

Magnesium sulphate has recently been suggested for use as an efficient analgesic adjuvant for post-operative pain in the field of anaesthesia. [10] Its analgesic effect appears to be related to the control of calcium entry into cells [11] or antagonistic activity on central nervous system N - methyl - D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors. [12,13] Magnesium sulphate reduces the noxious stimulus - induced somatic, autonomic, and endocrine responses. Magnesium is also recognised to have anti - inflammatory properties [14], which can lessen pain sensitivity in both the central and peripheral nervous systems. [15]

Additionally, postoperative shivering is reported to be less common when magnesium sulphate is used. [16,17] Shivering is thought to enhance catecholamine release, lactic acidosis risk, hypoxemia, and oxygen demand. [18] Additionally, magnesium sulphate may lessen the likelihood of nausea and vomiting. [19] Magnesium sulphate directly inhibits the smooth muscle of the heart and the blood vessels. It directly inhibits the release of catecholamines from the adrenal medulla and peripheral adrenergic terminals as well as their receptors. As a result, lower cardiac output and vascular tone lead to hypotension and decreased pulmonary vascular resistance. [20,21] In some ways, it has a sedative effect.

Material and Methods

Institutional ethics committee approval was taken after a review meeting.

Sampling Technique: Simple Random Sampling Method using a closed envelope.

Study Design: Observational Study with control group for comparison.

Study Population: This study includes ASA I & II patients in the age group of 20 to 65 years undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated using the effect sizes from the previously published study (Revi N. et al. international journal of basic and clinical pharmacology 2003) and with the help of following formula:

$$(Z_{\alpha} + Z_{\beta})\sigma$$

$$(PerGroup) = 2[Z_{\alpha}]^2$$

Sample size according to this formula is 25.15 \square 25 (Minimum Per Group) i. e Total 50 (Minimum).

In this trial, patients were observed as they received a bolus dose of 50 mg/kg of magnesium sulphate intravenously in 100 ml of normal saline over the course of 15 minutes to decrease postoperative pain

following spinal anaesthesia for lower limb orthopaedic procedures. The time at which patient complaints of pain postoperatively was noted and the total analgesic requirement in 24 hours were noted. The incidence of complications like hypotension, sedation, shivering, pruritus, nausea and vomiting were noted in these patients. Magnesium Sulphate infusion is expected to decrease analgesic requirement in the first 24 hrs and also decrease incidence of shivering, nausea and vomiting. The incidence of complications like hypotension and sedation is expected to be low. An observational study was done on 25 patients who are randomly selected to receive Magnesium Sulphate. These observations were compared with those of 25 patients who did not receive magnesium sulphate. The decision to use Magnesium Sulphate or not was according to randomisation using a closed envelope method by a consultant anaesthesiologist not involved with the observations. The observer was totally blinded to this decision and received this information after the full data was collected to formulate the conclusion. This study was completed over a period of 7 months.

Statistical Data Analysis: The data on continuous variables is presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) across two study groups. The inter - group statistical comparison of distribution of categorical variables is tested using Chi - Square test or Fisher's exact probability test. The inter - group statistical comparison of means of continuous variables is done using independent sample t test. p-values less than 0.0 are considered to be statistically significant. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for MS Windows is used to statistically evaluate all of the data.

Inclusion Criteria:

- 1) Patients between the age group of 20 and 65 years.
- 2) ASA Grade I & II

Exclusion Criteria:

- 1) Patients with cardiovascular, hepatic or renal dysfunction.
- 2) Patient having a known allergy to Magnesium Sulphate.
- 3) All patients who are on calcium channel blockers.
- 4) Patients in which spinal anaesthesia is contraindicated.

Methodology

Following a thorough explanation of the trial, all patients gave signed informed consent. All patients underwent a thorough physical examination, a complete history taking, and standard investiga-

tions. In accordance with the typical NPO protocols, the patients were kept fasting. Pre -induction parameters of BP, pulse and SpO2 were noted. Spinal anaesthesia was injected into the L3 - L4 or L4 - L5 interspace while the patient was sitting. After puncturing the dura with a 26 G Quincke's needle, hyperbaric 0.5% Bupivacaine solution 3 ml was injected intrathecally. Time at which spinal anaesthesia was given was noted. 100 ml normal saline bottles were given IV over a period of 15 minutes by the guide. Some had Magnesium Sulphate in the dose of 50 mg/kg. The observer was unaware of the contents. After the observational study was finished and the outcomes were compared, the code's solution was disclosed.

If the mean arterial pressure decreased 20% from baseline or the systolic blood pressure dropped to less than 90 mm Hg, ephedrine 6 mg was injected intravenously. If heart rate dropped to less than 45 beats per minute, 0.6 mg of atropine was injected intravenously. It was documented if the patient ever had hypotension or sedation.

Incidence of nausea, vomiting, shivering and pruritus in the postoperative period was recorded. Time at which patient started moving his legs and time at which patient first complained of pain (VAS score > 3) [Figure 6] was noted.

Rescue analgesics given in the first 6 hours of the surgery were noted. Patients were followed up for 24 hrs in the ward for the total analgesic requirement.

Assessment Protocol:

- T1: Time at which spinal anaesthesia was given.

- T2: Time when the patient started moving his legs (motor action of spinal anaesthesia wears off)
- T3: Time at which patient complained of pain and VAS score > 3
- T2-T1: Time of duration of action of spinal anaesthesia.
- T3-T1: Time to rescue analgesia
- 24 hours analgesic requirement (All the analgesics given to the patient in 24 hrs were noted)

Rescue analgesia was given with I.V Paracetamol 1gmalone or along with I.V Tramadol 50mg I.V in 100 ml normal saline if the patient had shivering. Any incidence of shivering, nausea and vomiting were noted. Total analgesics required at the end of 24 hours were noted.

Results

In our analysis, there was no statistically significant difference between group A (cases) and group B in terms of age, sex, BMI, comorbidities, ASA grade, or the type of surgery.

The difference between group A (cases) and group B's mean time to rescue analgesia was statistically significant. Comparing group A (case) to group B (control), the mean time to rescue analgesia [T3 - T1] is longer in group A (case) [444±130] than in group B [287± 55]. This was consistently seen across a range of age groups and surgical specialties. There is a statistically significant difference here. (P - value < 0.05 for all). [Table 1]

Table 1: Inter-group comparison of mean time to rescue analgesia.

Time (Mins)	Group A [Case] (n=25)		Group B [Control] (n=25)		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T3- T1 [Time to rescue analgesia]	444.0	130.0	287.0	55.0	0.001***
Values are mean and SD, P -value by independent sample t test. P -value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant. ***P - value < 0.001.					

In the first six hours, group A (case) requires less rescue analgesia than group B (control), and this difference is statistically significant. (P - value < 0.05) In the first six hours following surgery, 36% of patients in group A (case) and 88% of patients in group B (control) needed analgesics. [Table 2]

Table 2: Inter-group distribution of requirement of rescue analgesia in first 6-hrs.

Requirement of rescue Analgesia in first 6 -hrs	Group A [Case] (n=25)		Group B [Control] (n=25)		P- value
	n	%	n	%	
Not required	16	64.0	3	12.0	0.001***
Required	9	36.0	22	88.0	
Total	25	100.0	25	100.0	
Values are n (% of cases), P- value by Chi-Square test. P-value < 0.05 is considered To be statistically significant. ***P -value < 0.001.					

The mean spinal anaesthesia action time [T2 - T1] in group A (case) [245±22] is longer than in group B (control) [209±23], which is statistically significant. With the exception of TKR, the mean duration of action of spinal anaesthesia in Group A

(Case) is longer than in Group B (Control) across a range of age groups and surgical procedures, and the difference is statistically significant. (P - value < 0.05 for all). [Table 3]

Table 3: Inter-group comparison of mean duration of action of spinal anaesthesia [T2T1] in various types of surgeries

Time (Mins)	Surgery group	Group A [Case] (n=25)		Group B [Control] (n=25)		P- value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T2- T1 [Time of Duration of action of Spinal anaesthesia]	Fracture	246	22	214	25	0.003**
	ALR	248	21	202	21	0.001***
	TKR	230	23	210	24	0.323 ^{NS}

Values are mean and SD, P - value by independent sample t test. P - value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant. *P-value < 0.05, **P-value < 0.01, ***P- value < 0.001, NS – Statistically non - significant.

20% (n=5) of the patients in group A (case) and 20% (n=5) of the patients in group B experienced episodes of hypotension, in comparison, when it comes to complications. Sedation was seen in 16% (n=4) of patients in group A (case) and 4% (n=1) of patients in group B. Shivering episodes were experienced by 16% (n=4) of patients in group A (case)

and 16% (n=4) of patients in group B. 12% (n=3) of patients in group B and 4% (n=1) of patients in group A (case) experienced nausea episodes, respectively. In group A (case), 4% (n=1) of patients experienced vomiting, and group B (control), 4% (n=1). [figure 1]

In both groups, none of the patients developed pruritus. The incidence of complications like hypotension, sedation, shivering, nausea, vomiting, and pruritus was the same in both groups and did not differ statistically. (P - value > 0.05 for all)

Discussion

Anti-nociceptive action of Magnesium sulphate is mediated by antagonism of NMDA receptors and decreased calcium mediated neurotransmitter release. The central sensitization of pain has been shown to decrease and the duration of the sensory block to lengthen when NMDA receptors are blocked. Magnesium inhibits the release of acetylcholine from motor nerve terminals and directly lowers the excitability of muscle fibre membranes,

both of which contribute to a motor blockade.

In our study, patients who underwent spinal anaesthesia for lower limb orthopaedic procedures were assessed for the analgesic efficacy of intravenous magnesium sulphate. 25 patients which received IV Magnesium Sulphate in the dose of 50 mg/kg in 100 ml Normal Saline, Group A (case) were compared to 25 patients which received 100 ml Normal saline, Group B (control) for requirement of analgesic drugs in 24 hours of postoperative period. The time to rescue analgesia was also observed. Comparisons between the two groups were made for problems such hypotension, sedation, nausea, vomiting, shivering, and pruritus.

Analgesic Effect

In Group A, the time to rescue analgesia was extended. In the first six hours following surgery, only 36% of patients in Group A (the case) required analgesics, compared to 88% of patients in Group B (the control), who required analgesics in the same time period. It was statistically significant that there was a difference in the need for analgesics.

Group A (the case) needed fewer analgesics than group B (the control) in the first 24 hours following surgery, and the difference was statistically significant. The dosages of injection Diclofenac, injectable Paracetamol, and opioids needed by Group B were higher. Tramadol, Diclofenac, and Paracetamol injections successfully treated the patients in Group A (case). When analgesic requirement was compared in various types of orthopaedic surgeries, our study found that the 24 hours analgesic requirement for lower limb fracture surgeries and arthroscopic ligament repair was less in group A (case) as compared to group B (control). This difference was statistically significant. There was no statistically significant difference in the 24 hours analgesic requirement for Total Knee Arthroplasty in Group A (case) and Group B (control) but clinical significance needs to be evaluated further.

Complications

Complications such hypotension, sedation, nausea, vomiting, shivering, and pruritus were looked for in both groups of patients.

All groups had an identical incidence of hypotension. 20% of patients in group A and 20% of patients in group B experienced episodes of hypotension, which were successfully treated with injection ephedrine 6 mg IV. Magnesium sulphate didn't make hypotension more common in our study.

Sedation occurred more frequently in Group A (the case) of our study than in Group B (the control), but this difference was not statistically significant.

Cases in Group A (cases) felt less nauseous than those in Group B. (control). This difference was clinically important even if it was not statistically significant.

Vomiting was prevalent in both groups on an equal level.

In our study, post-operative shivering was reported by 16% of patients in Group A and 16% of patients in Group B. They were kept under control for 15 minutes by an injection of tramadol 50 mg IV administered in 100 ml of normal saline. Both groups experienced shivering on a comparable level. Magnesium sulphate did not significantly improve shivering in our trial.

Both groups did not exhibit pruritus.

Limitations

The limitations of our study were as follows–

- 1) In ability to measure serum magnesium levels
- 2) In ability to use Patient control analgesia (PCA) for postoperative analgesia
- 3) Prolonged follow up of patients after the first 24 hrs of postoperative period was not done.
- 4) Comparison of Magnesium with other agents was not studied.

Conclusion

Our research showed that, the patients receiving spinal anaesthesia for lower limb orthopaedic procedures benefit from a bolus dosage of 50 mg/kg IV magnesium sulphate with minimal incidence of complications. This mode of attenuating postoperative pain can be effectively and safely used in low resource settings.

References

1. Olapour AR, Mohtadi AR, Soltanzadeh M, Ghomeishi A, Akhondzadeh R, Jafari M. The effect of intravenous magnesium sulfate versus intravenous sufentanil on the duration of analgesia and postoperative pain in patients with Tibia Fracture. *Anesthesiology and pain medicine*. 2017 Apr; 7 (2).
2. Sivrikaya GU. Multi modal Analgesia for Postoperative Pain Management in: Pain management – current issues and opinions. Edited by Gabor BR and Carl E. Istanbul, Intech 2012; 177 - 210.
3. Rashiq S, Dick BD. Post - surgical pain syndromes: a review for the non - pain specialist. *Canadian Journal of Anesthesia/Journal canadien d'anesthésie*. 2014 Feb 1; 61 (2): 123 - 30.
4. Hwang JY, NaHS, Jeon YT, RoYJ, KimCS, DoSH. IV infusion of magnesium sulphate during spinal anaesthesia improves postoperative analgesia. *British journal of anaesthesia*. 2010 Jan 1; 104 (1): 89 - 93.
5. Macintyre PE. Safety and efficacy of patient - controlled analgesia. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2001 Jul 1; 87 (1): 36 - 46.
6. Wong H, Benzon H. Epidural opioid analgesia. In: Benzon H, Raja S, Molloy RE, Strichartz G, eds. *Essentials of Pain Medicine and Regional Anesthesia*. New York, USA. Churchill Livingstone, 1999: 159 - 163.
7. Twycross R. Opioids. In: Wall P, Melzack R, eds. *Textbook of Pain*. Edinburgh, UK: Churchill Livingstone, 1999: 1187 - 1214.
8. Page S. Opioid receptors. In: Benzon H, Raja S, Molloy RE, Strichartz G, eds. *Essentials of Pain Medicine and Regional Anesthesia*. New York, USA. Churchill Livingstone, 1999: 48 - 50.
9. Kehlet H, Rung GW, Callesen T. Postoperative

- opioid analgesia: time for a reconsideration? *J Clin Anesth* 1996; 8: 441 - 445
10. Albrecht E, Kirkham KR, Liu SS, Brull R. Peri-operative intravenous administration of magnesium sulphate and postoperative pain: a meta-analysis. *Anaesthesia*.2013 Jan; 68 (1):79 - 90.
 11. Iseri LT, French JH. Magnesium: nature's physiologic calcium blocker. *The American heart journal*.1984;108 (1): 188 - 93.
 12. Feria M, Abad F, Sánchez A, Abreu P. Magnesium sulphate injected subcutaneously suppresses autotomy in peripherally deafferented rats. *Pain*.1993Jun 1;53(3):287-93.
 13. Woolf, C. J.; Thompson, S. W. The induction and maintenance of central sensitization is dependent on n methyl - d - aspartic acid receptor activation; implications for the treatment of post - injury pain hypersensitivity states. *Pain* 1991, 44, 293–299
 14. Aryana P, Rajaei S, Bagheri A, Karimi F, Dabbagh A. Acute effect of intravenous administration of magnesium sulfate on serum levels of interleukin - 6 and tumor necrosis factor - α in patients undergoing elective coronary bypass graft with cardiopulmonary bypass. *Anesthesiology and Pain Medicine*.2014 Aug;4 (3).
 15. Kidd BL, Urban LA. Mechanisms of inflammatory pain. *British journal of anaesthesia*.2001 Jul 1; 87 (1):3 -11.
 16. Park SM, Mangat HS, Berger K, Rosengart AJ. Efficacy spectrum of anti-shivering medications: meta - analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Critical care medicine*.2012 Nov 1; 40 (11): 3 070 - 82.
 17. Kizilirmak S, Karakas SE, Akca O, Ozkan T, YavruA, Pembeci K, Sessler DI, Telci L. Magnesium sulfate stops post anesthetic shivering. *Annals of the NewYork Academy of Sciences - Paper Edition*.1997 Mar 15; 813: 799 - 806.
 18. Alfonsi P. Post anaesthetic shivering. Epidemiology, pathophysiology and approaches to prevention and management. *Minervaanestesiologica*.2003May;69(5):438.
 19. Ryu JH, Kang MH, Park KS, Do SH. Effects of magnesium sulphate on intraoperative anaesthetic requirements and postoperative analgesia in gynaecology patients receiving total intravenous anaesthesia. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*.2008 Mar1; 100 (3): 397 - 403.
 20. O'Riordan JA. Pheochromocytomas and anaesthesia. *International anesthesiology clinics* .1997 Sep1;35(4): 99 -128.
 21. Zheng D, Upton RN, Ludbrook GL, Martinez A. Acute cardiovascular effects of magnesium and their relationship to systemic and myocardial magnesium concentrations after short infusion in awake sheep. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*.2001 Jun 1; 297 (3): 1176 - 83